

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University CoARA Action Plan

Preamble

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University is a classical university in the western part of Ukraine and the largest university in the Precarpathian region. The university is a member of international consortia, including the European University Association, the Warsaw University and Ukrainian Universities Consortium, the Baltic and Ukrainian Universities Consortium, the Magna Charta Universitatum Consortium, and an associate member of the European Digital UniverCity (EDUC) alliance and the UNIVERSEH space universities consortium. Oriented towards European education standards, the university comprises an extensive system of structural units, including 78 departments, 12 faculties, 3 institutes, and 1 college. The university conducts educational and research activities in various fields, including management, physical education, natural sciences, history, political science, international relations, physics, engineering, tourism, philology, mathematics, computer science, psychology, foreign languages, pedagogy, economics, law, and arts. Additionally, the university actively collaborates with scientific and educational institutions, implementing innovative projects and initiatives aimed at developing scientific potential and improving the quality of education.

By signing the CoARA Agreement, the university undertakes ten main commitments. The PNU action plan outlines the following steps and initiatives aimed at fulfilling these obligations, enhancing the institution's role in international cooperation and academic excellence.

Starting Point

Action Step 1

Action Step 2

Action Step 3

Reflect on your strategy and change approach

Creation a committee dedicated to identifying and promoting diverse contributions to research.

Conducting a discussion to determine the main principles that are a priority in the approach to reforming the university.

Development a plan that describes the implementation of reforms in accordance with defined principles. Create a monitoring and evaluation system for tracking.

Involve your institutional community in the change process

Organizing focus groups and discussions with researchers at different career stages to gather opinions and ideas on reform issues.

Consultations with deans and directors to take into account their needs and perspectives (SHAPE disciplines).

Development a system for effective dissemination of successful practices of EDUC universities.

Identify key challenges to address

Conducting a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis of the current research evaluation system.

Determination of the authority, resources and capabilities of the university to solve the identified challenges.

Development of specific strategies for each identified problem, taking into account available resources.

Operational action plan for a 5-year time frame

	Action Step 1	Action Step 2	Action Step 3
1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	1.1. Forming a committee dedicated to identifying and promoting diverse contributions to research	1.2. Develop guidelines that require researchers to credit all contributions to research outputs, using tools like CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy).	1.3. Develop and implement Responsible Research Assessment Policies by creating a new policy to align with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and CoARA commitments.
Timeframe	Q4 2024	Q4 2025	Q3 2026
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	2.2 Implementation qualitative evaluation mechanisms in funding instruments for research projects, research initiatives, and fields (Seed Project).	2.2. Providing training for researchers and research managers on broader assessment approaches, review appraisal guidance to ensure recognition of peer review contributions, and offer guidance on open peer review and peer review credit systems.	
Timeframe	Q4 2026	Ongoing commitment	
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal-and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	3.1. Promoting the use of alternative metrics, such as Altmetric scores, alongside traditional metrics for a more comprehensive assessment.	3.2. Integrating COARA (Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment) principles into existing researcher development regulations, ensuring these principles are reflected in relevant university policies and guidelines.	3.3. Monitoring staff awareness of the evaluation of responsible research by surveying researchers every two years.
Timeframe	Q1 2026	Q1 2026	Q3 2026
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	4.1. Implement internal assessment mechanisms that prioritize the university's mission, values, and strategic goals over external rankings.		
Timeframe	Q3 2025		
5. Commit resources to	5.1. Creating a detailed resource allocation plan to implementing	5.2. Development and delivering	

reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to	research assessment reforms.	internal training programs for research-enabling and professional services staff on responsible research assessment.
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Timeframe	Q3 2025	Ongoing commitment
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6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes	6.1. Conduct an institutional and national mapping exercise to analyze current research assessment criteria, tools, and processes, identifying gaps and opportunities.	6.2. Revise current research assessment criteria to align with CoARA commitments, ensuring fairness, accountability and comprehensiveness of assessment.	6.3. Piloting alternative criteria and assessment tools, such as descriptive resume formats, competency-based resume formats, and evidence-based resume formats.
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Timeframe	Q4 2025	Q4 2025	Q4 2026
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7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use	7.1. Update and share information through various channels such as university websites, library services and research portals about changes in research assessment.	7.2. Providing guidance on best practices for conducting fair, objective, and evidence-based assessments of research contributions and achievements.	7.3. Promoting opportunities for research evaluation projects to apply for funding and actively participate in national and international forums for sharing best practices and learning in other institutions.
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Timeframe	Ongoing commitment	Q4 2025	Ongoing commitment
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8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	8.1. Joining online platforms and communities of practice where members can exchange ideas, resources, and success stories related to research assessment reform (OpenUP).	8.2. Organization of symposiums, conferences, and workshops, that bring together stakeholders from diverse backgrounds to share experiences and insights on effective research assessment strategies.
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Timeframe	Q3 2024	Ongoing commitment
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9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments	9.1. Dissemination of information about the organization's research assessment processes, including publication of the action plan and its	9.2. Reporting back on research assessment progress and updates in relevant group meetings and committees to keep stakeholders informed.
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Timeframe	Q1 2025	Annually
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	10.1. Active engagement with national and international research assessment processes and organizations such as CoARA to align internal practice with the latest principles and evidence in research assessment.	10.2. Creation of a schedule for regular review of assessment criteria, tools and processes.
Timeframe	Ongoing commitment	Q1 2025

Contacts

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University
 57 Shevchenko Str., Ivano-Frankivsk, 76018, Ukraine
 tel.: (+380-342)75-23-51
 e-mail: office@pnu.edu.ua
 web-page: <https://pnu.edu.ua>